

leaves. Although all crop stages are susceptible, the infestation rate and feeding are heavier in nurseries about to be transplanted and in the early transplanted crop. During heavy incidence, almost all leaves are infested. Feeding symptoms are narrow linear holes in the interveinal areas that leave the veins intact. Such holes are

distributed along the entire leaf lamina and resemble those made by grasshoppers.

A field trial was conducted to determine suitable insecticides for controlling crickets as well as other insects. Six insecticide granules were tried at 2 levels:

- Carbofuran at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha
- Phorate at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha

- Mephosfolan at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha
- Disulfoton at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha
- Quinalphos at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha
- Chlordimeform hydrochloride at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha.

Of these carbofuran at 1.0 kg a.i./ha was the most effective in pest control, followed by phorate at 2.0 kg a.i./ha. ■

Occurrence of the rice ear-cutting caterpillar in the Punjab of Pakistan

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The rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Pseudaletia unipuncta* has never been a serious rice pest in the Punjab Province of Pakistan. The first observation of serious damage was reported on berseem fodder (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) in 1972. That crop is sown after rice harvest in the rice tract of Pakistan. At that time only a few larvae and pupae are observed in rice stubble. An unusual upsurge of the pest was noticed in the area of the Institute in October and November. Attacks of the pest were also recorded in Narang and Kamoke areas (Sheikhupura District). The pest attacked the rice crop when routine insecticide applications were halted after the third week of September.

Observations of ear-cutting caterpillars, Punjab, Pakistan.

Variety	Visual assessment of damaged panicles (%)	Insects (av no./hill)
BR2360-6-5-1-10	95	5.4
BR51-46-5	90	4.6
IET6073	70	1.8
BP919-24-7-1	50	2.2
B541-B-KN-22-7-2	30	3.0
B441-B-126-3-2-1	15	1.2
B541-B-KN58-5-3	10	1.6
IET3363	5	1.4

The larvae damaged some varieties considerably. The insect preferred semidwarf varieties, particularly those that were relatively green. Panicles of such varieties were completely denuded.

Observations on the number of insects per hill were recorded in a field sown to different varieties. Five hills per sample were checked. The results are in the table.

From 1.2 to 5.4 insects/hill, averaging

2.6/hill. were present (see table). As expected, varieties with more insects were damaged more; the soil surface was completely covered with cut panicles and grains.

In a preliminary trial, dusting the crop with a mixture of BHC (0.25 kg a.i./ha) + DDT (0.75 kg a.i./ha) killed 95% of the larvae within 24 hours of the application. Water was completely drained before dusting. ■

Two subterranean pests of upland rice in Papua New Guinea

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Two rice pests newly identified in Papua New Guinea can severely damage upland rice in the seedling and tillering stages.

Infestation symptoms are similar to those of kresek, a systemic symptom caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*. Seedlings that are attacked at an early age die, and more mature plants that are attacked have fewer tillers and fewer spikelets per panicle. The younger tillers are affected most severely. Widespread infestation

can destroy as much as 90% of the crop.

Caenoblissus pilosus (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae), a chinch bug previously reported from the western Carolines, is related to *Blissus* sp., a pest of maize, small grains, and turf grasses.

In appearance and life cycle it is similar to *Blissus* sp. At the youngest stage it is 0.7 mm long. At adult stage, the insect is about 3 mm long, with silver wings on a black body. At the juvenile stage it is red with black markings.

Chinch bugs inhabit the root zone immediately adjacent to the base of the plant within 1 or 2 cm of the soil surface. They may be visible on the soil surface in the early morning or late afternoon.

Mealy bugs (family Pseudococcidae)

have also been observed in most fields that are attacked by chinch bugs. They are often found on nearby plants, but not on the same plants as chinch bugs. Ants, which tend the mealy bugs, are usually present on the soil surface at the base of the plant.

The adult mealy bug is 2.5 cm long and off-white to pink. Both the chinch bug and the mealy bug damage the plant by extracting moisture and nutrients from the roots. They also attack maize and sorghum, but because the infestation level is lower, damage symptoms are not visible.

Puspalum sp. and other soft-stemmed grasses are alternate hosts of the chinch bug.